

Kinetic Study of Cu(II)-Catalysed Oxidation of Lactic Acid by the Peroxodisulphate Ion

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Cu(II)-catalysed oxidation of lactic acid by the peroxodisulphate ion is reported. Kinetic orders in the oxidant, catalyst and reductant concentration have been evaluated. The rate law $-d[S_2O_8]^{2-}/dt = k[S_2O_8]^{1.5}[Lactic\ acid]^{0.4}[Cu(II)]^{0.3}$ has been interpreted in terms of a most likely mechanism involving oxidation of the Cu(II)-lactate complex by the $SO_4^{\cdot -}$ and OH^{\cdot} radical-ions by parallel reaction pathways.

Cu(II) has been reported as a catalyst in a few peroxodisulphate oxidations¹⁻⁶. Kinetic studies of these oxidations suggest that catalysis occurs where the organic substrate can serve as a ligand (*loc. cit.*). Lactic acid is known to form complex with copper(II)⁷⁻¹². This reaction was therefore selected for a kinetic study to throw light on the mechanism operative in copper(II) catalysed $S_2O_8^{2-}$ oxidations. Uncatalysed and Ag(I) catalysed oxidations of lactic acid have already been reported¹³⁻¹⁴.

Experimental

All chemicals used were either BDH 'AnalaR' or E. Merck G.R. samples. Reactant solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. Kinetics were followed by estimating residual peroxodisulphate iodometrically at different intervals of time¹⁵.

The $S_2O_8^{2-}$ equivalents of Cu(II) concentration (5×10^{-4} moles/litre) kept in any experiment in terms of titre volume (of 0.04 N) have been subtracted from the observed titre volume values to obtain (a-x). [At lower Cu(II) concentrations it was not necessary].

The first order rate constants in peroxodisulphate concentration were calculated by the established expression given below :

$$k_1 = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$$

where 'a' and 'a-x' are the concentrations of peroxodisulphate initially and after time 't' respectively. Rates were calculated by the familiar expression dx/dt where 'dx' is the amount of reduced peroxodisulphate in a certain interval of time 'dt'.

Result

Stoichiometry : The stoichiometry was verified by allowing a solution containing 0.01M lactic acid, 0.04M $K_2S_2O_8$ and 2.0×10^{-4} M $CuSO_4$ to react for 3 hr at 55°. The decrease in peroxodisulphate concentration was ascertained and a blank was run

simultaneously. Results conform to the equation

Product analysis : The oxidative degradation of lactic acid is represented by :

This reaction is a comparatively fast reaction. On prolonged standing it oxidises to acetic acid and carbon dioxide *via* acetaldehyde as follows :

Therefore, only acetaldehyde and carbon dioxide has been detected in the reaction mixture. Acetaldehyde was identified in the reaction mixture by conversion into 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone by its spot test¹⁶. $CO_2^{\cdot -}$ radical reduces mercuric chloride and converts itself into CO_2 which supports the formation of carbon dioxide during the reaction¹⁷.

The rate law : The results of the kinetic run at 55° are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1— $[LACTIC\ ACID]_0 = 0.01M$, $[K_2S_2O_8]_0 = 0.02M$, $[CuSO_4]_0 = 0.0001M$

Time (sec)	Volume of 0.04N $Na_2S_2O_8$ (ml)	$(S_2O_8^{2-})$ (moles/l)	$10^3 R$ moles $l^{-1} sec^{-1}$	$10^3 k_1$ (sec^{-1})
0	4.95	0.0198	—	—
900	4.63	0.0185	14.2	7.41
1800	4.37	0.0175	12.9	6.92*
2700	3.41	0.0136	22.8	13.8
3600	2.89	0.0116	22.8	15.0
4500	2.55	0.0102	21.3	14.8
5400	2.28	0.0091	19.8	14.7
6300	2.09	0.0084	18.2	13.7
7200	1.99	0.0080	16.5	12.7
Average Value			18.6	14.1
Slope Value				13.8

* Mean calculated hereafter

It appears that the first order peroxodisulphate decomposition is disturbed initially for a period

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ranging from 900-2700 sec whereafter a fair constancy in k is obtained. The concentration-time curve is initially S-shaped, typical of autocatalytic reactions. Such kinetic features are reproduced at other concentrations.

Rate as a function of initial concentrations of reactants: Peroxodisulphate dependence: The rate (R) and the first order constants (k) at different initial concentrations of peroxodisulphate are summarised in Table 2.

TABLE 2—[LACTIC ACID]₀=0.02M, [Cu₂SO₄]₀=0.0001M
TEMP. 55°

[S ₂ O ₈ ²⁻] moles/l	10 ⁴ k sec ⁻¹	10 ⁷ R moles l ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	10 ⁴ Rate (S ₂ O ₈ ²⁻) ^{1.2}
0.005	12.4	4.71	2.7
0.010	17.8	10.9	2.7
0.015	22.5	17.7	2.7
0.020	24.0	24.7	2.7
0.030	26.0	43.8	2.9
0.040	26.5	58.3	2.8

The rate is not strictly first order in S₂O₈²⁻ and the plot of R against [S₂O₈²⁻]^{1.2} is linear (Fig. 1) satisfying the equation

$$-d[S_2O_8^{2-}]/dt = k' [S_2O_8^{2-}]^{1.2} \quad \dots (I)$$

where k' is a function of the reducible substrate and catalyst concentrations.

Fig. 1. 1.2 Order dependence in S₂O₈ concentration

Lactic acid dependence: Table 3 shows the effect of varying concentration of lactic acid on the rate of reaction.

TABLE 3—[K₂S₂O₈]₀=0.02M, [CuSO₄]₀=0.0001M, TEMP. 55°

[Lactic acid] ₀ moles/l	10 ⁷ R moles l ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	10 ⁴ Rate [Lactic acid] ^{0.4}
0.005	15.0	1.2
0.01	18.5	1.2
0.015	23.5	1.3
0.02	24.7	1.2
0.025	28.3	1.2
0.03	30.7	1.2
0.04	31.5	1.2

The specific rate constant values increase with increase in the initial lactic acid concentration over an eight fold range. Fig. 2 shows that the plot of the overall rate R against lactic acid concentration is not linear. Evidently, the order with respect to lactic acid is not unity. The order when calculated between the two acid concentrations (0.01M and 0.02M) by the Van't Hoff's differential method gives m=0.4. Fig. 2 was replotted with the lactic

Fig. 2

acid concentration raised to the power of 0.4 and a straight line was obtained (Fig. 3). The intercept of this line at zero lactic acid concentration is 1.5 × 10⁻⁷ moles l⁻¹ sec⁻¹ which approximates with the rate of thermal decomposition of 0.02M peroxodisulphate in presence of 1 × 10⁻⁴M CuSO₄ (temp. 55°) and in the absence of a reducing substrate.

The overall rate of the reaction may, therefore, be expressed as

$$-d[S_2O_8^{2-}]/dt = k [S_2O_8^{2-}]^{1.2} [Lactic acid]^{0.4} \quad \dots (II)$$

where k is a function of Cu(II) concentration.

Copper(II) dependence: Table 4 summarises the results showing the influence of varying concentrations of Cu(II) on the rate of reaction.

The variation of the overall rate with change of Cu(II) concentration over a range of 0.0001M to 0.001M and as computed from the results shown

Fig. 3. Fractional order dependence in lactic acid concentration.

 TABLE 4—[LACTIC ACID]₀=[K₂S₂O₈]₀=0.02M, TEMP. 55°

[CuSO ₄] ₀ moles/l	10 ⁷ R moles l ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	10 ⁶ k' sec ⁻¹	10 ⁴ k' [CuSO ₄] ₀ ^{0.3}
0.00001	12.9	11.8	3.7
0.00010	24.7	24.0	3.8
0.00025	27.3	26.2	3.2
0.00040	30.2	30.2	3.2
0.00050	31.8	33.8	3.3
0.00100	38.8	42.7	3.4

in the above Table and Fig. 4 reveal the rate law to be fractional (0.3) in Cu(II). The intercept of line at zero CuSO₄ concentration k is $3.3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ sec}^{-1}$, which compares well with the rate constant value for the uncatalysed oxidation reaction. The complete rate law may then be expressed by

$$-d[S_2O_8^{2-}]/dt = [S_2O_8^{2-}]^{1.2} [\text{Lactic Acid}]^{0.4} [\text{Cu(II)}]^{0.3} \quad \dots \text{ (III)}$$

 Fig. 4. Fractional order dependence in CuSO₄ concentration.

Temperature dependence: The effect of temperature on k was studied in the range 45-60° and the results are shown in Table 5.

 TABLE 5—[LACTIC ACID]₀=[K₂S₂O₈]₀=0.02M, [CuSO₄]₀=0.0001M

Temp °C	45	50	55	60
10 ⁶ k ₁ (sec ⁻¹)	2.42	7.90	24.0	58.7

The Arrhenius plot is linear and conforms to the equation

$$k = 5.25 \times 10^{24} \exp. (-42.82 RT) \text{ sec}^{-1}.$$

Influence of acids, salts and gases: These are recorded in Table 6.

 TABLE 6—[K₂S₂O₈]₀=[LACTIC ACID]₀=0.02M, [CuSO₄]₀=0.0001M, TEMP. 55°

10 ⁶ k(sec ⁻¹) 10 ⁷ R (moles l ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹)	0.05M		0.05M		Atmosphere	
	H ₂ SO ₄	K ₂ SO ₄	Sod. acetate	O ₂	CO ₂	
	24.0	22.2	27.5	2.57	5.62	31.3
	24.7	24.2	27.7	3.68	10.0	32.0

H⁺ ion, sodium acetate and O₂ gas inhibit the reaction rate while K⁺ ions and CO₂ gas have a catalysing effect.

Discussion

For the interpretation of the kinetic data reported herein few points bear significance.

In an excess amount of lactic acid almost all the copper(II) should be Cu(II)-lactate complex in the solution⁷⁻⁹ as is evidenced by the pH variation and conductivity studies.

Measurements reveal that the rate of peroxodisulphate disappearance approximates to 1.2 in [S₂O₈²⁻]₀ while a fractional order dependence in lactate and Cu(II) is observed. The rate determining step, therefore, involves peroxodisulphate or some species produced therefrom. Since a bimolecular reaction between the oxidant and the catalyst is ruled out on kinetic grounds^{1,6} a reasonable mechanism which accounts for the faster oxidation rate in presence of Cu(II), [kCu(II)-cat/k] is 7.3], may have the following steps:

It is believed that reaction (2) is fairly slow followed by rapid sequences (3), (4), with the production of CO_2^- (Seq. 3), the higher rate $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ decomposition is explained by the reaction (5). That CO_2^- is produced is evident from the fact that the system reduces Hg(II) chloride¹⁷ and oxygen inhibits the reaction rate [oxygen is known to inhibit certain reaction involving CO_2^- radicals; $\text{O}_2 + \text{CO}_2^- \rightarrow \text{O}_2\text{CO}_2^-$. (*loc. cit.*)].

Moreover, it is also reported that the metal ion after forming a complex with the organic substrate¹⁷⁻¹⁹ decays to produce CO_2^- radical. The CO_2^- radical, being as reactive as SO_4^- , is energetically capable of reacting with other reagents present in the solution or with peroxodisulphate ion (*loc. cit.*). Thus it propagates the chains.

In the above mechanism it is postulated that the Cu(II) -lactate complex is oxidised to the Cu(III) oxidation state by the SO_4^- radical (reaction 2). This is identical with the mechanism proposed by Kovata¹⁹, Allen² and Kimura⁴. It is also generally known that the complex formation leads to favourable conditions for the oxidation of metal ion. This is presumably the reason that SO_4^- oxidises Cu(II) -lactate but do not oxidise lactic acid⁷. Subsequently, Cu(III)L decays via reaction (3) producing CO_2^- radicals.

The pH variation study during course of the oxidation in presence of Cu(II) shows steady decrease for initial period (45 min), unlike that obtained without copper (Fig. 5) which is accounted for by Seq. (4). This period coincides with the disturbed first order kinetics of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ decomposition.

By the steady state treatment, one can derive $-\text{dc}_{\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}}/\text{dt} = k_5 \text{c}_{\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}} [k_1 \pm (k_1^2 + 4k_1 k_2 k_6/k_6 \text{Cu(II)L})^{1/2} / 2k_6]$... (IV)

Fig. 5. pH variation.

which simplifies to

$$-\text{dc}_{\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}}/\text{dt} = (4k_1 k_2 k_6/k_6)^{1/2} [\text{Cu(II)L}]^{1/2} (\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}) \dots (V)$$

if k_1 is small.

The derived rate law is first order in peroxodisulphate and involves the Cu(II) -lactate concentration which can be taken as representing Cu(II) concentration. The rate law then shows the rate to be linear in $[\text{Cu(II)}]^{0.5}$. The experimental value of 0.3 in Cu(II) concentration obviously suggests a parallel oxidation pathway involving the Cu(II) -complex. This perhaps could be the oxidation of the Cu(II) -complex by the hydroxyl radicals also produced as under :

It is reasonable to assume oxidation by these radical as well.

Both reactions (2) and (8) are competitive being equally probable^{6,20}. This results in a lower effective concentration of Cu(II) and approximately to $[\text{Cu(II)}]^{0.5}$.

The rate of $[\text{Cu(II)}]_0$ to $[\text{lactic acid}]_0$ varies from 1 : 20 to 1 : 50 and therefore practically all Cu(II) is complexed. However, lactic acid molecules remain in excess. It is quite probable that these lactic acid molecules are also oxidised directly. This finds support from the plot (Fig. 4) showing dependence in Cu(II) concentration which does not pass through the origin. Evidently, lactic acid is also oxidised simultaneously without being in the complexed form by the reaction scheme proposed for the uncatalysed reaction (*loc. cit.*) involving sequence (9).

which would explain the fractional dependence in lactic acid concentration.

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